

Clinical Signs and Symptoms in Manicurists Exposed to Chemical Substances In Orizaba-Córdoba, Veracruz, México

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Occupational exposure to chemical substances in manicure salons poses a health risk.

Objective: To identify clinical signs and symptoms in manicure workers and their relationship with the use of chemical substances in the Orizaba-Córdoba, Veracruz.

Material and Methods: Cross-sectional analytical study (n = 51). A bivariate analysis was performed, and a p-value ≤ 0.05 was considered statistically significant using STATA version 13.

Results: All participants were women, with 72% aged between 18 and 33 years and with 1 to 5 years of job seniority. A statistically significant association was found between dermatological manifestations and duration of exposure (p = 0.046); and between ocular manifestations and number of services per day (p = 0.046), use of protective eyewear (p = 0.044), salon size (p = 0.040), and use of solvents (p = 0.047).

Conclusions: Clinical manifestations in manicure workers were associated with solvent use and working conditions.

KEYWORDS: Manicurists, chemical substances, occupational health, clinical profile.

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INTRODUCTION

In recent decades, the beauty salon sector has experienced remarkable growth, particularly in nail design services. This expansion has led to a significant increase in the number of manicurists who, in the course of their activities, are exposed to various chemical substances contained in products such as nail polishes, removers, acrylics, gels, and adhesives. These products often contain potentially toxic volatile compounds, including acrylates, formaldehyde, acetone, among others (6,14,16,22).

Several studies have documented elevated concentrations of chemical compounds in beauty salon environments, including benzene, toluene, ethylbenzene, and formaldehyde, with reported levels exceeding permissible exposure limits (8,10,13). Factors such as inadequate ventilation, duration of exposure to chemical substances, number of services

performed per day, and insufficient use of personal protective equipment directly influence exposure levels (9,11,17).

In Mexico, the Mexican Institute of Social Security (IMSS) is the main social security institution, and through its occupational health services, it seeks to prevent work-related diseases (30).

Workplaces that use chemical substances are required to comply with Official Mexican Standard NOM-010-STPS-2014, *Chemical agents contaminating the work environment—Recognition, evaluation, and control*, which establishes procedures and measures to prevent health risks among personnel occupationally exposed to chemical contaminants in the workplace (31).

The objective of this study was to identify the clinical profile of manicurists exposed to chemical substances in the Orizaba-Córdoba region.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A cross-sectional analytical study was conducted including 51 manicurists working in beauty salons affiliated with the Mexican Institute of Social Security. Inclusion criteria were being manicure workers employed in beauty salons located in the Orizaba-Córdoba region, Veracruz; having active affiliation with the Mexican Institute of Social Security (IMSS); and having signed informed consent to participate in the study.

Data were collected through an occupational medical history. The variables studied included:

- **Sociodemographic variables:** age, sex, educational level, and history of chronic-degenerative diseases.
- **Occupational characteristics:** job seniority, daily working hours and rest days, number of services per day, activities performed, type of nail application technique used, type of workplace ventilation (natural [windows] or mechanical [exhaust systems]), use of personal protective equipment, daily exposure time to chemical products, and number of workers in the beauty salon.
- **Clinical manifestations:** presence of respiratory symptoms (sneezing, cough, rhinorrhea, nasal itching), dermatological symptoms (pruritus, dry or cracked skin, rash, depigmentation), ocular symptoms (itching, red eye, tearing, foreign body sensation), and neurological symptoms (headache and dizziness).

A univariate analysis was performed to identify outliers. Categorical variables were described as frequencies and percentages, and numerical variables were grouped into categories for better data management.

To determine associations between variables, the study population was divided into two groups based on whether participants reported clinical manifestations during the work shift (yes/no). Subsequently, a bivariate analysis was conducted using Fisher's exact test to determine associations between variables. Statistical significance was set at $p \leq 0.05$. The database was managed using Excel version 2506 (build 16.0.18925.20076), and statistical analysis was performed using STATA version 13.

The study was classified as minimal-risk research. Data confidentiality was ensured, and informed consent was obtained from all participants, following the ethical principles established by the Declaration of Helsinki and current national regulations.

RESULTS

A total of 51 beauty salon workers providing manicure services were included, all of whom were female. Most participants were between 18 and 30 years of age (72.5%) and had completed upper secondary education (66.7%), and all were apparently healthy (Table 1). Regarding working conditions, 64.7% had job seniority of 1 to 5 years, with working days longer than 8 hours (80.3%), and Sunday was

the main rest day (90.2%). More than five clients per day were attended by 62.7% of participants, and in 76.5% of cases, more than three workers were employed in the same beauty salon.

A total of 88.2% reported using some type of personal protective equipment, including three-layer face masks, safety glasses, and nitrile gloves; however, these were not used simultaneously. Additionally, face masks were reused for up to two days. A total of 64.7% reported daily contact with chemical substances for 7 to 8 hours. Natural ventilation was the most common type (80.4%), and 54.9% of workplaces had an area smaller than 20 m² (Table 2).

Regarding activities performed in beauty salons, most workers carried out more than two tasks in addition to manicure services, such as administrative duties, hair cutting, and hair washing. In some salons, hair bleaching and coloring services were also provided, representing additional chemical exposure.

The most frequent nail application techniques were acrylic and gel, which together accounted for 74.51% of workers. The most commonly used chemical substances were nail polish removers (74.51%), mainly acetone; nail polishes (74.51%), whose main components included glycol methacrylate, trimethylolpropane triacrylate, N,N-dimethylacrylamide, butyl acetate, isopropyl alcohol, and ethyl acetate; solvents (66.67%), including 1-hydroxy-4-(p-toluidino) anthraquinone, ethyl methacrylate, 2-hydroxypropyl methacrylate, and acrylic acid; and hardeners (60.78%), primarily composed of ethyl acetate (Table 3). It is noteworthy that many products lacked ingredient labeling and safety data sheets, and most were of Asian origin.

The most frequently reported dermatological manifestations were pruritus and dry or cracked skin (78.42%). Respiratory symptoms, mainly sneezing and/or nasal itching, were reported by 70.59% of participants. Ocular symptoms, particularly foreign body sensation, were reported by 23.53%, and 35.29% of the population reported headache or dizziness during chemical substance use (Table 4).

To determine the relationship between clinical manifestations during the work shift and exposure to chemical substances, a bivariate analysis was performed. For dermatological manifestations, participants with any symptom were included in the "yes" group (n = 40), and those without symptoms in the "no" group (n = 11). A statistically significant association was found between daily exposure time and dermatological manifestations ($p = 0.046$) (Table 5).

For respiratory manifestations, participants with symptoms were included in the "yes" group (n = 42) and those without in the "no" group (n = 9); no statistically significant associations were identified. Similarly, no significant associations were found for neurological manifestations (headache and dizziness).

For ocular manifestations, participants reporting symptoms were included in the "yes" group (n = 28), and those without symptoms in the "no" group (n = 23). Statistically significant

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associations were identified between ocular manifestations and number of daily services ($p = 0.046$), solvent use ($p = 0.047$), workplace area $<20 \text{ m}^2$ ($p = 0.040$), and use of protective eyewear ($p = 0.044$) (Table 6).

DISCUSSION

This study provides evidence of clinical manifestations associated with occupational exposure to chemical substances among manicure workers in the Orizaba-Córdoba region. The findings highlight a high prevalence of dermatological and ocular symptoms, with a significant association between exposure duration and the presence of cutaneous manifestations.

Similar results have been reported in international studies. Lamplugh et al. documented dermatological and ocular symptoms among beauty salon workers in Colorado related to elevated concentrations of volatile organic compounds (VOCs) (6). Likewise, Tran et al. reported a high frequency of dermal symptoms among manicurists exposed to organic solvents in Vietnam (12). Gatica-Ortega et al. described cases of allergic contact dermatitis associated with acrylate use in long-lasting nail polishes, reinforcing the clinical relevance of the dermatological findings in this study (33).

The work environment in beauty salons has also been identified as a risk factor. Baghani et al. reported that reduced salon size and inadequate ventilation increase airborne contaminant concentrations (15). Pavilonis et al. identified elevated carbon dioxide levels in nail salons in New York as an indicator of poor ventilation, similar to the conditions observed in this study, where natural ventilation without forced extraction predominated (16). In this study, a salon area $<20 \text{ m}^2$ was associated with ocular manifestations, likely due to reduced ventilation and increased accumulation of chemical substances in indoor air.

Regarding chemical products, a high frequency of use of nail polish removers, polishes, and solvents was observed. Many of these compounds are organic solvents that evaporate easily and accumulate in poorly ventilated spaces, posing a significant occupational health risk even when individual concentrations do not exceed permissible exposure limits.

One of the reasons for evaluating this population was to identify the compounds handled, frequency of use, and whether health effects were already present. A next step will be to evaluate indoor air concentrations of relevant chemical substances in beauty salons to better characterize exposure levels and associated risks.

Insufficient and improper use of personal protective equipment represents a risk factor for the development of occupational diseases, as previously described by Ana et al. among salon workers in Nigeria (19). In this study, the use of protective eyewear reduced ocular effects, although it was not specifically designed for solvent exposure. Participants reported using PPE mainly for COVID-19 protection, protection against solid particles, or during specific tasks,

showing limited awareness of the need for protection against organic solvent exposure.

Study limitations include low participation rates resulting in a small sample size and the inability to assess chronic effects. Future research should focus on environmental measurements of chemical substances in indoor air and long-term health outcomes.

CONCLUSIONS

The results demonstrate a significant association between ocular and dermatological clinical manifestations and occupational characteristics among manicurists exposed to chemical substances. These findings underscore the need to implement preventive strategies and improve working conditions in beauty salons to reduce chemical exposure. Future studies should include environmental monitoring to assess chemical exposure levels and chronic health effects associated with solvent exposure.

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TABLE 1. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY POPULATION

Variable	n = 51	%
Sex		
Male	0	0
Female	51	100
Age		
18–30 years	37	72.52
31–40 years	9	17.64
>40 years	5	9.80
Educational level		
Basic education	8	15.69
Upper secondary education	34	66.67
Higher education	9	17.65
Chronic-degenerative diseases		
Dermatological history	10	19.61
Respiratory history	8	15.69
Neurological history	1	1.96
Diabetes mellitus	1	1.96
Arterial hypertension	1	1.96
None	30	58.82

TABLE 2. OCCUPATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS OF MANICURE WORKERS

Variable	n = 51	%
Job seniority		
1–5 years	33	64.71
>5 years	18	35.28
Working hours		
<8 hours/day	10	20.61
>8 hours/day	41	80.39
Rest day		
Sunday	46	90.20
Thursday	3	5.88
Tuesday	1	1.96
Saturday	1	1.96
Clients per day		
<5 services	19	37.25
>5 services	32	62.74
Number of workers per salon		
<3	12	23.53
>3	39	76.46
Use of personal protective equipment (PPE)		
No	6	11.76
Yes	45	88.24
Daily exposure time to chemical substances		

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3 to <7 hours	5	9.80
7-8 hours	33	64.71
>8 hours	13	25.49

TABLE 2 (CONTINUED). OCCUPATIONAL CHARACTERISTICS

Variable	n = 51	%
Salon area		
<20 m ²	28	54.90
>20 m ²	23	45.10
Ventilation type		
Mechanical	10	19.61
Natural	41	80.39

TABLE 3. TYPES OF CHEMICAL SUBSTANCES USED BY MANICURE WORKERS

Variable	n = 51	%
Nail polish remover		
No	13	25.49
Yes	38	74.51
Nail polish		
No	13	25.49
Yes	38	74.51
Base coat		
No	23	45.10
Yes	28	54.90
Hardener		
No	20	39.22
Yes	31	60.78
Solvents		
No	17	33.33
Yes	34	66.67

TABLE 4. CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS DURING THE WORK SHIFT

Variable	n = 51	%
Dermatological symptoms		
Pruritus / dry or cracked skin	40	78.42
None	11	21.57
Respiratory symptoms		
Sneezing / nasal itching	36	70.59
Rhinorrhea	3	5.88
Nasal congestion / sneezing	1	1.96
Cough / sneezing	1	1.96
Nasal congestion	1	1.96
Cough	0	0
None	9	17.65
Ocular symptoms		

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Foreign body sensation	12	23.53
Pruritus / foreign body sensation	7	13.73
Pruritus	4	7.84
Red eye	3	5.88
Red eye / tearing	1	1.96
Pruritus / tearing	1	1.96
None	23	45.10
Neurological symptoms		
Headache / dizziness	18	35.29
None	33	64.71

TABLE 5. DERMATOLOGICAL CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS DURING THE WORK SHIFT

Variable	No (n=11) %	Yes (n=40) %	p-value
Age			
18–30 years	72.73	72.50	0.401
31–40 years	27.27	15.00	
>40 years	0	12.50	
Job seniority			
1–5 years	63.64	65.00	1.000
>5 years	36.36	35.00	
Working hours			
<8 hours	18.18	20.00	1.000
>8 hours	81.82	80.00	
Clients per day			
<5	36.36	37.50	1.000
>5	63.64	62.50	
Daily exposure time*			
<7 hours	100.00	67.50	0.046
>8 hours	0	32.50	

TABLE 6. OCULAR CLINICAL MANIFESTATIONS DURING THE WORK SHIFT

Variable	No (n=23) %	Yes (n=28) %	p-value
Clients per day*			
<5	52.17	25.00	0.046
>5	47.83	75.00	
Use of protective eyewear*			
No	95.65	75.00	0.044
Yes	4.35	25.00	
Salon area*			
<20 m ²	39.13	67.86	0.040
>20 m ²	60.87	32.14	
Solvent use*			
No	47.83	21.43	0.047
Yes	52.17	78.57	